

Clinical data integration strategies for multicentre studies

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Abstract. Multicentre health studies are important to increase the impact of medical research findings due to the number of subjects that they can engage. To simplify the execution of these studies, the data-sharing process should be effortless, for instance, using interoperable databases. However, achieving this interoperability is still an ongoing research topic. In the first stage of this work, we propose methodologies to optimise the harmonisation pipelines of health databases, considering the OMOP CDM as the destination schema. In the following stage, aiming to enrich the information stored in OMOP CDM databases, we have investigated solutions to extract clinical concepts from unstructured narratives. In the final stage, we aimed to simplify the protocol execution of multicentre studies, by proposing novel solutions for facilitating the discovery of databases. The developed solutions are currently being used in European projects aiming to create federated networks of health databases across Europe.

Keywords: Health data; Database profiling; Data integration; Text mining; OMOP CDM

1 Introduction

The continuous demand for better health diagnostics and treatment has encouraged numerous clinical research investigations, including observational studies and clinical trials [1]. In clinical trials, patients are usually divided into groups (*e.g.* active and placebo), to study the effectiveness of the treatment for a particular clinical condition [2]. In this case, there is the direct intervention with the patients, *e.g.*, administration of a drug or therapeutic procedures. However, this approach may not be always the most adequate, *e.g.* addressing research questions in plastic surgery through randomized controlled trials is often subject to ethical constraints [3]. In observational studies, researchers do not perform any active intervention with patients, and exposure occurs naturally or through other factors [1]. Here, medical researchers limit themselves to documenting the relationship between the exposure and the outcome in the study [2].

Observational studies follow different strategies and are established by defining a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria for the subjects involved, as well as several

features that are identified and observed over time [4]. Some initiatives reuse the data already collected in medical institutions to conduct observational studies. This practice saves time and enables pre-verification of the number of subjects before starting the analysis [5]. However, in specific diseases, it is necessary to collect information about the selected subjects. In these situations, the data are recorded based on the study guidelines and different solutions can be used to store the data, for instance, the institutional Electronic Health Record (EHR) system [6]. The dependence on technical teams is a major barrier when there is a need to extract data for analysis. Many other ethical and technical issues are raised when one wants to combine datasets from distinct organizations. This is the case of multicenter studies that aim to increase the population size, the power of the statistical evidence, and thereby the study's impact [7].

Integrating multiple data sources is not just a technological problem. There are some Extraction, Transformation and Load (ETL) tools capable of performing this task using large amounts of data. The non-technical problem of this aggregation is the data domain, *i.e.*, identifying the concepts in the data and combine correctly the information associated with them that was extracted from multiple sources. Healthcare databases belong to one of the domains in which this is a concerning problem, due to the variety of concepts to represent similar procedures and medical terms. Solving these problems is helpful to optimize studies, but sharing patient-level data still raises some privacy issues, due to legal, ethical, and regulatory requirements [8]. Patient data are very sensitive, and disruption of this privacy can have dramatic consequences for individuals, healthcare providers and subgroups within society [9]. Besides, the legislation may be different in each country, which makes it difficult to define a protocol that fits all the institutions involved [10]. This is another challenge, which requires finding a solution that allows the analysis of multiple data sources, or parts of these, without exposing sensitive data.

Researchers are driven by the potential impact of multicenter studies to look for more reliable and reusable solutions to combine knowledge from distributed health datasets [1]. Organizations and methodologies were established to explore clinical databases by reusing existent data [5]. One of these efforts aims to create a strategy to reuse EHR databases using a homogeneous schema, to facilitate the interoperability between databases. This integration is currently possible using open-source frameworks that help support the whole process [1].

The research objectives of this work can be paraphrased into several questions focused in addressing specific problems. We recognize that multicenter medical studies may raise additional issues that will not be considered in this work, mainly due to the data types used on these. For instance, research studies based on biomarkers that are correlated with DNA information, or studies primarily focused on using medical images. Therefore, to achieve a scenario capable of supporting distributed health studies using multiple data sources from distinct institutions, we limited the scope to EHR databases. This objective will be accomplished by answering the following research questions:

1. *How to execute a database query over a network of heterogeneous health databases?* The lack of interoperability is the main problem in this scenario. An ecosystem with heterogeneous databases may not share the same data schema, which invalidates the query-sharing. Besides this problem, the healthcare domain contains

huge amounts of medical concepts, that may differ between institutions, at the national or international level. A methodology to harmonize such databases is required, which converts them into an interoperable format. This process may have different stages and components, and some of them will be automatized aiming to reduce the cost and time of executing this procedure. This may result in a new software solution.

2. *How to enrich patients' health history using information available in clinical notes?* The free format of this type of information raises several challenges in terms of named-entity recognition and normalization. Currently, the research lines focused on NLP, may lead to new solutions that can enrich this field. In this work, we aim to investigate a solution capable of improving the quality of information stored in the relational databases. This solution will be a software solution capable of processing clinical free text and storing this information in a relational database, following the harmonization principles defined in the ETL procedures for EHR databases.

3. *How to select the most adequate health databases for a specific research study?* This question can be addressed from different perspectives. However, by correlating it with the previous statements, we identified that the main problems medical researchers meet are: i) the discovery of databases of interest; and ii) the access to those databases without violating privacy policies and ethical regulations. The solution to these problems is too complex to be solved by a software application alone. To answer this question, it is necessary to create an ecosystem of tools and methodologies, in which data owners can feel confident in sharing characteristics about their databases, while researchers can have enough information to select the databases that fit better their needs. Therefore, the solution proposed for this problem will be a portal that integrates: i) a web catalogue of database characteristics; ii) tools to visualize and compare these characteristics; and iii) tools for orchestrating distributed studies.

In this paper, we present an extended overview of a PhD thesis focused on enriching information extraction pipelines in clinical decision support systems. The main objective of this work was to investigate a new strategy to use medical data from distributed databases to conduct multicenter health studies.

2 Contribution to Technological Innovation For Connected Cyber Physical Spaces

One of the most important parts of a medical study is the patients' information correlated to the study scope. The patient's characteristics are crucial to the success of medical studies since it is estimated that up to 50% of trials are not completed due to insufficient enrollment [11]. When collecting these characteristics, the procedure is achieved to a specific goal, resulting in distinct data types. For instance, distinct medical tests can be performed on the subjects, such as blood analysis, medical imaging, and electrocardiogram, to identify any health issue. This information contributes to the medical history of each person, which can be a valuable insight for future diagnostics or prognostics [12]. However, the digital data formats for those records can be different.

To address the challenge of managing different digital data formats for medical records, technological innovation for connected cyber-physical spaces can play a crucial role. By integrating several medical data sources, healthcare researchers can collect or questioning different institutions based on a study scope. This has the potential of increasing the number of subjects in the study, improving its findings. Overall, technological innovation for connected cyber-physical spaces can support the integration and analysis of patient data, leading to improved healthcare outcomes and better understanding of human health.

3 Contribution to Technological Innovation for Connected Cyber Physical Spaces

The secondary use of medical data to conduct research studies has become a common practice. These studies have provided complementary support to generate new insights and knowledge, namely in pragmatic trials using records collected from routine clinical care visits, comparative effectiveness studies or patient-centered outcomes research [13]. These data were not primarily generated to support research or secondary analysis. This concept refers to the use of data for purposes other than those that it was originally collected [14]. However, over the last few years, the clinical research community recognized that recruiting patients to record their medical characteristics over time is challenging. Although this practice is required in some types of studies, medical research is currently not limited to them. Therefore, this section provides a brief overview of the most relevant data types in the medical domain.

3.1 Electronic health records

An EHR is a digital version of the data collected about a patient. Hospitals usually have a EHR system to make the information available in real-time to the health professionals of the institution [15]. Besides patient data, there is an amount of additional information regarding patients' medical conditions that are also stored in such systems. EHR aims to simplify the data management and data exchange within the institution, between different services, resulting in higher quality and safer care for patients.

Some of the data stored in these systems follow a tabular structure, following the principles of relational databases [16]. Although there are some efforts in having interoperable databases supporting the EHR systems, each vendor has its own data schema. Over the last years, several EHR standards were developed, namely the CEN ISO 13606 [17], OpenEHR [18], OMOP CDM from OHDSI [5, 19] and HL7 standards (CIMI, HL7-CDA HL7-FHIR) [16]. The HL7 standards were proposed to simplify the transfer of clinical and administrative data between software applications used by different healthcare providers. They define guidelines and methodologies to support the communication between various healthcare systems [20].

Utilizing the data from the EHR system to answer healthcare questions differs from the traditional approach based on collecting data after defining a question [15]. The tabular data can help medical researchers conduct different types of studies, namely by identifying patient populations with specific healthcare interventions and outcomes, e.g., related to drug exposure, procedures, and conditions, among others. The parameters available to characterize these patient populations are various, including demographic information, healthcare delivery, utilization and cost, morbidities, treatments and sequence of treatment, and disease natural history.

Although EHR has been used for many years, as well as the idea of secondary use of this data, the process of reutilizing its data still raises some challenges. These challenges include limitations of processing ability [21, 22], interoperability [23, 24], inability to extract the required information [25, 26], and security and privacy concerns [27].

EHR can be a formal strategy for federating all biomedical data into a single integrated view. Some information may not be possible to represent in this format, such as medical images or omics data. However, this tabular format already contains valuable information to be used for conducting medical studies.

3.2 Clinical notes

EHR systems can have repositories of non-tabular patients' information, e.g., clinical notes. The text data contained in these notes is typically subdivided into main categories, depending on whether they are structured or not. The structured notes, as the name indicates, integrate some structured format, for instance, a form. Examples of this data are the diagnosis forms or the laboratory analysis results. Alternatively, unstructured notes refer to notes that contain free-text, for instance, some of the physician's notes transcripts [28]. Free text notes are characterized by their vast variability, especially due to their heterogeneity. EHR contains agglomerates of different types of medical narratives (for progress, admission, operative, primary care, and discharge, among others), with different dimensions (from very short to very long) [29]. Structuring the information available in medical narratives is challenging due to this reason, but also because those are often ungrammatical. They contain short telegraphic sentences, plenty of misspellings, and are filled with abbreviations. In some cases, these abbreviations refer to local dialectal shorthand expressions, which may overload the use of acronyms, *i.e.*, the same group of letters with different meanings [28].

One strategy to introduce some kind of structure in these notes is making use of pseudo-templates or integrating tabular data into the narratives, for instance, the laboratory results. This pseudo-structure is not generalized, and nothing ensures that this is used in all narratives present in the system. Besides, the adoption can vary between physicians, services, or institutions [28]. A different attempt to increase the readability of free-text notes was through the adoption of standard lexicons to encode the information present in the narratives [30].

Nonetheless, since clinical text poses great interest, some approaches have been developed for extracting relevant information. Even though this process has historically consisted of having clinical experts manually review clinical notes, a

process that cannot scale with the growing rate of generation of medical data [31], much research has been made during the past years in domains such as clinical NLP to create systems capable of automatically annotating and summarizing important text content in clinical notes [32].

The use of unprocessed narratives for conducting multicenter studies raises several challenges, namely regarding patients' privacy and data interoperability. Mapping the medical concepts to their standard definition solves the latter issue but raises other challenges since the mapping task can be extremely complex and time-consuming. Moreover, it is acknowledged that the challenging nature of the free text can make it difficult to develop automatic information extraction solutions for clinical text [33].

4 Semi-automatic translation of data sources into a common schema

The lack of flexibility in users' collaboration during the design and definition of the ETL pipelines is a problem for some application domains. For instance, in the medical scenario, when clinical data needs to be harmonized into a common data schema, this requires collaboration between the technical teams and the medical researchers [34]. This collaboration is required in different stages: i) design; ii) implementation; and iii) validation. In each stage, there are some challenges that we addressed in this work.

4.1 Methodology for cohort harmonization

We proposed methodology based on the ETL principles. During the extraction stage, the chosen source data is obtained by pulling it from one or multiple data sources. The main goal of this stage is to get the data from the source systems without interfering with their usual performance. This is a sensitive undertaking in health databases, as the EHR cannot be overloaded due to the data extraction procedure. Furthermore, clinical studies were exported to a tabular format, which do not require direct interaction with the system used to collect the patient data.

Out of all the stages, the transformation stage is the most complex component. This stage requires the mapping of the source database into the target schema, as well as the harmonization of the content. For a data source, this procedure requires a full mapping, which is time-consuming and requires specialized entities to validate the mappings. Custom operations on the data may be necessary, depending on the source of the data. Clinical databases contain a broad range of clinical concepts that require harmonization using standard vocabularies. Although certain parts of this stage have been automated, we still rely on manual validation by a specialized health professional to ensure that all mapped data is accurate.

The loading stage completes the process by inserting the processed data into the target database, which can then be accessed using analytical tools. These databases are populated with pseudo-anonymous data, allowing clinical studies to be conducted without violating patients' privacy rights. Furthermore, when data is migrated to this

schema, the original data can also be validated, and inconsistencies can be detected. The pipeline includes quality mechanisms that verify whether loaded data adhere to the rule attributes for each standard concept.

4.2 Proposed tools

The technical components of the proposed methodology were first implemented in a Python-based tool [1, 35]. This tool includes the stages of the ETL operations, *i.e.* the workflow from the cohort's raw data into the OMOP CDM database is divided into the three ETL stages, as presented in Figure 1. In this implementation, we split these stages to enable their execution in an isolated manner. We also adopted some open-source tools to support some of the stages of this workflow. WhiteRabbit and Usagi are tools from the OHDSI ETL ecosystem. WhiteRabbit is responsible for collecting information about the data sources' structure, namely columns and attributes. While Usagi is used to map concepts into their standard definition. This last offers an intuitive GUI that helps the medical specialist to validate these mappings.

Figure 1 The migration workflow from raw data to the OMOP CDM structure, using the proposed methodology combined with the ETL OHDSI tools. This workflow is divided into three main stages, having two processes running in parallel (marked in a red dashed line). The first stage extracts cohort information and loads it into the system. The transformation stage performs all the defined operations over the raw data using the mappings mixed with the ontology rules. Finally, the loading stage inserts the data in the database, producing a migration report which indicates all the problems with the original raw data [1].

The implementation of some components raised some challenges due to the data sensibility of the proposed use case. Dealing with medical data requires a deep understanding of the data source to perform accurate harmonization. Besides, there is another challenging task that requires custom operations on each cohort's raw data. This is because the data collection strategy was not standardized, making it difficult to work with the original data. This lack of interoperability when recording the data complicated the implementation of the migration workflow.

The data quality is another advantage of using this workflow. When a ETL procedure is finished, a report is generated that includes statistical information about the data migrated, namely inconsistencies in the source data. This information can help data owners to identify these issues before conducting studies with the data.

BIcenter is a ETL tool capable of covers some of the existent limitations currently found in building and managing ETL tasks in multi-institution environments [36]. This web-based tool can simplify the development of ETL workflows. With its intuitive GUI, the tool can help users without technical expertise to understand such workflows. BIcenter replicates the Kettle features in an HTML5 browser and simplifies some of the procedures in Kettle that may require deep technical knowledge of this tool.

The use of BIcenter leveraged the proposed methodology to new possibilities, leading to a collaborative and multi-institutional environment. BIcenter was initially developed to have different roles assigned to different institutions. This strategy allows the use of a single installation to define the migration pipelines of all cohorts with the possibility of splitting users by institutions or cohorts. The existing RBAC mechanisms can support the sets of permissions to access the different features of the application. For instance, it allows specific users to visualize the results of each transformation or write them in the target database.

BIcenter-AD was proposed to be an extension of BIcenter applied to Alzheimer's disease datasets [37]. This tool provided a collaborative environment that was centralized in the ETL Task Editor. This workspace allows the definition of the ETL pipelines with all components required to harmonize Alzheimer's disease cohorts. The users with the role capable of editing ETL tasks can work collaboratively in the same workspace. Although these tools do not create real-time working sessions, the user-friendly environment can support users when they work collaboratively.

5 From unstructured text to ontology-based registers

In the previous section, we proposed different strategies to migrate heterogeneous data into a common data schema. Following this research direction, we identified some gaps in these ETL procedures regarding non-structured medical information.

5.1 Extract and harmonize drug mentions

The first proposal for extracting medical information from non-structured data was a two-stage workflow, denominated DrAC [38]. The initial stage of the workflow involves extracting prescriptions found in patients' clinical notes. Subsequently, the extracted information is harmonized into standard definitions during the second stage, before being stored in a shared database schema known as the OMOP CDM.

The system initially receives clinical notes as input, reads their content and stores it according to a fixed structure. To implement this reader, a factory programming pattern was used. This simplifies the adoption of this tool a new dataset of clinical notes is used. Once the clinical notes have been read, the annotator is employed to extract the medication entities present in each note. The resulting annotations are then stored and subject to post-processing. The tool used for this was Neji, a flexible and modular framework for text processing and annotation [39].

To set up Neji as a medication annotator, we first extracted three drug-related medical terminologies from the UMLS Metathesaurus [40]: RxNorm, DrugBank and AOD. These terminologies encompass several semantic types and groups. Therefore, we narrowed the scope of the dictionaries by filtering them and only retaining entries from the “Chemicals & Drugs” semantic group. These dictionaries were imported to the Neji server and a new service was configured for this. Once all of these notes were loaded into the system, the Neji web service was employed to annotate medication entities in each note and the extracted information was stored.

Once this is completed, all the extracted mentions were stored in a matrix structured by patient and drug. Each cell holds information on a drug mentioned, namely the strength, dosage, and route. The reason for storing extracted data in this particular format lies in the fact that the resulting structure is similar to that already used in cohort studies, greatly simplifying the process of harmonizing this information into an OMOP CDM database.

5.2 Multi-language Concept Normalization

One of the challenges posed by ETL procedures is the significant effort required to map original concepts to their standard definitions. Although there are various automatic mapping solutions available to assist with this task, their complexity increases when working with multilingual databases, resulting in a substantial manual effort for translation and mapping. In this work, we also proposed a strategy that combines text mining with language detection techniques to optimize migration pipelines [41]. This system is intended to be integrated into existing migration workflows.

Our proposal employs two open-source tools to: i) provide a user interface for mapping validation; and ii) supply a web collaborative platform to manage the ontologies utilized in our proposal. Usagi was used as the interface for validating the mappings. It offers suggestive mappings based on word similarity through a simple and intuitive interface that non-technical teams can use to validate the mappings. While Usagi's suggestions only compare concepts with the standard vocabulary, leading to many incorrect suggestions that require manual modification, the user interface is user-friendly and can be reused for our proposed approach. Currently, it is used in several migration workflows, including those proposed in the previous section.

6 Scalable database profiling for multicenter studies

One of the challenges when reusing health databases for research is the correct selection of the data sources. This is a complex problem since it requires strategies to characterize data sources without revealing their content, and platforms for disseminating the databases' characteristics [42, 43]. For the database characterization issue, there are already some guidelines when dealing with this type of data. Depending on the project or institution's policies, the data owners can share

aggregated information about their data. This can provide a summarization of the patients in the databases. Other characteristics can also be provided, namely data governance policies and contact details. These summarization guidelines are not standard and may differ depending on the context. For instance, a community focused on studying Alzheimer’s Disease would have datasets with different characteristics compared with a more generic domain [44].

Profiling databases (or fingerprinting) is the action of representing a database using a set of characteristics that combined can create a singular conception of the database. Defining these characteristics raises some issues that vary depending on the project scope. While these issues have complex solutions, we propose a different strategy to help the discovery of medical databases. It aims to provide enough information about the databases, that can characterize them at a deeper level, without sharing sensitive information. Figure 2 represents the main idea of the concept of this summarization, which is defined as fingerprinting.

Figure 2 The concept of fingerprinting databases focuses on extracting characterizes from databases of the same type.

6.1 Framework for profiling databases

The MONTRA 2 framework was developed as a solution for enabling biomedical data sharing through the creation of web-based environments for research purposes. The database catalogue can be considered one of the core features of MONTRA 2. In this catalogue, it is represented each database through the concept of fingerprinting, as was already described. Therefore, the data owners can define the catalogue structure that better fits their needs in that scope, and the system generates the web catalogue based on that file. The skeleton structure is flexible and contains fields (questions) to be filled by the data owners. Several questions can be aggregated in a “QuestionSet”, creating a hierarchical data representation. Each question can store different types of data, for instance, dates, numbers, strings, multiple-choice values, geographic location, among others. These fields, which represent the metadata about the health

databases in the catalogue, are used for free text search, advanced search, dataset comparison, and other features of the catalogue.

MONTRA 2 was implemented to also support the creation of an environment to integrate distinct tools in a centralized platform. The goal of this paradigm was to provide the researchers with a workplace with all required tools to: i) compare and identify the databases of interest for clinical studies; ii) streamline a study over the network; and iii) retrieve the results and aggregate them. All these tools are protected under a federated SSO mechanism with profile verification. MONTRA 2 is currently used to support different other projects. The system has three instances in production, to support different platforms, namely the EHDEN Portal, EMIF Catalogue and MSDA Portal.

6.2 Explore distributed patient-level databases

The methodology proposed to streamline the execution of multicenter studies is based on MONTRA 2. To accomplish this, we developed an additional tool that was integrated in MONTRA 2 as a plugin [45]. It aims to simplify the execution of health studies as well as centralize and coordinate the operations between all the entities involved. The proposed system, designated as Study Manager, adopted the same technologies used in MONTRA 2, namely Django in its core. To simplify the integration between systems, this tool was implemented to be compliant with the MONTRA SDK, following a MVC software pattern. This pattern segregates the application logic into three main elements: i) the model, responsible for handling the data storage; ii) the view, that generates the data representation for the client; and iii) the controller, which contains the business layer.

With all the proposed solutions in the previous sections, including MONTRA 2 framework, the process of conducting multicenter medical studies is currently a reality. Health and life science researchers have identified several opportunities in sharing data. These opportunities can only be achieved if researchers can share data between them. The strategy proposed in this work empowers them with bigger data sets for each study, which increases the impact of their findings. However, different governmental issues were raised with this idea. Therefore, the proposed strategies aim to facilitate the exploration of patient-level databases, while minimizing the risk of violating the patient's privacy.

7 Results and Discussion

Enriching information extraction pipelines in clinical decision support systems is a research topic that can be addressed from different points of view. In this work, we tried to enrich these pipelines starting by working on the foundations of clinical decision support systems. We recognised that to increase the quality of the treatments, researchers need to study the impact of new drugs, or the efficiency of current treatments. These findings can originate new treatment protocols that can be integrated into the decision-support systems of healthcare institutions. Therefore, in

this work, we focused on creating methodologies and tools to help medical researchers conduct more impactful findings, to improve the source of these systems.

We started by specifying the scope of this work, based on the biomedical data formats that we could use. Motivated by EHDEN project, we focused this work on EHR relational data, that we tried to supplement with data extracted from medical narratives. Then, in the later stage, after defining strategies to have an interoperable network of data sources, we proposed solutions to support research using these data sources. In short, we presented several software solutions to integrate biomedical data, and the final product is a platform that facilitates the exploration of this information across databases [46].

The first hypothesis addressed the lack of interoperability between health databases. However, as we find during this work, the problem was not the lack of standard solutions to interconnect these databases. Instead, the problem was the effort required to adopt one of these standards. To answer this problem, we proposed solutions to simplify the migration of EHR data to one of the standard data schemas currently used in medical studies. We validated these solutions using heterogeneous cohorts of patients' data suffering from Alzheimer's disease, combining at the end 6,669 subjects and 172 clinical concepts. The interoperability was ensured by converting data sources to the OMOP CDM schema [1].

The second hypothesis was about enriching the information stored in the databases, using unstructured data present in clinical narratives. For this, we proposed a solution capable of extracting medical concepts and storing them in an OMOP CDM database. Part of this solution is supported by the work done to answer the first hypothesis. We validated the proposed NLP strategies using scientific challenges, namely organized by n2c2 organization [38].

Finally, the third hypothesis was focused on finding the most adequate health databases for specific research studies. To answer this question, we have collaborated during this doctoral program with the EHDEN partners aiming to propose and adjust a solution based on real needs. The result was a flexible framework capable of being extended to support complementary tools. This work was validated in the context of the EHDEN project [46]. This portal currently contains information about 93 EHR databases, which are publicly accessible to all the 750 registered. Additionally, it also replaced old technologies that have supported the EMIF project in the past. This tool has been validated with thousands of users, with a huge impact on real-life environments since medical researcher can easily identify databases of interest to conduct multicenter studies.

8 Conclusions and future work

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With this research, we identified some future work and research directions, namely by analyzing some of the limitations of the proposed solutions. Herein, we present and discuss some of the possible research lines for future work:

1. Standardizing a fingerprinting schema: A lot of efforts have been conducted to ensure interoperability between data sources, as well as to publish their metadata to facilitate discovery. This resulted in several health database catalogues that cannot communicate and exchange information between them. There are already some initiatives to create federated catalogues in specific domains, however, this is only the beginning. Standard schemas and ontologies to federate this communication is a possible research direction to optimize the creation of health database catalogues.

2. Automatic definition of ETL workflows: Automatically establishing the mappings between the original data schema to the target is an open research direction that can be applied beyond the health domain. This can be simplified and focused on the medical domain, by using OMOP CDM as the target data schema. In this work, we proposed semi-automatic methodologies, but this proposal can be optimized at different levels.

3. Extending OMOP CDM to incorporate other data types: Over the years some initiatives tried to extend the OMOP CDM to incorporate more information. The adoption of these initiatives at a large scale fails due to several issues (ensuring data privacy in complex data formats, breaking the schema interoperability, and raising issues when sharing results, among others). Investing in this direction may leverage medical research to new levels, namely by allowing distributed studies using DICOM images, or genomic data.

4. Secure FAIR data: The goal of FAIR principles is to optimize the reuse of data. The principles emphasize machine-actionability, *i.e.*, the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention [47]. However, we identified a research line in this topic, by combining it with security, *i.e.* applying the FAIR principles following secure guidelines to ensure safe machine-to-machine communication.

Considering the increasing impact of technology in healthcare, along with the rapid developments in this field, we firmly believe in the importance of the presented research topics.

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